

Adaptive Backstepping Fractional-order Nonsingular Terminal Sliding Mode Control of the Continuous Polymerization Reactor

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Abstract

This paper proposes an adaptive backstepping fractional order nonsingular fast terminal sliding mode control (AB-FNTSMC) for a polymerization reactor subjected to model uncertainties and environmental disturbances. This controller ensures robust performance in both reaching and sliding mode phases. A fast terminal reaching law is employed to remove the chattering phenomena. An adaptation rules are used to update the upper bounds of the disturbances whose information are not required. A numerical simulation is deployed to evidence the superior performance of the AB-FNTSMC.

Keywords: Adaptive Control, Polymerization reactor, Fractional-order, Nonsingular Fast terminal sliding mode control.

1. Introduction

In polymer chemistry, polymerization is a process in which the reacting monomers combined to form a high molecular compound [1], [2]. Polymerization reactions take place in chemical reactors (batch, semi-batch or continuous reactors [3]) at expeditious rate and may result in explosions if not sufficiently regulated. As such, it is crucial to control the operating conditions of the reactor. The operating conditions include but not limited to monomer concentration, reaction rate, reactor temperature, coolant flow rate, initiator type, [4], [5].

The contamination of measurements by sensor noises, purity of products, variation in feed conditions and degree of mixing make polymerization reactions difficult to be controlled directly or monitored accurately [6]. The Automatic Continuous Online Monitoring of Polymerization reactions (ACOMP), gives the real-time measurements of the process dynamic states [7], [8], [9], [10]. The limitation of ACOMP is that it hardly measured the complete state vector. Therefore, an observer is required to measure all the states [11].

An Extended Kalman Filter (EKF) is the most commonly used measurement method in chemical industries [12], [13]. In [14], an EKF has been used to measure the states of Methyl-Methacrylate (MMA) copolymerization. In [15], the melt index (MI) of propylene polymerization process has been estimated using least squares support vector machine. In [16], an EKF has been applied to measure the biogas composition in a Continuous Stirred Tank Reactor (CSTR). A hierarchical EKF has been used to estimate the kinetic parameters in the production of ethylene-propylenediene polymer [17].

In order to compensate the uncertainties and external disturbances deteriorating the operations of chemical processes, sliding mode control (SMC) strategies are employed. In [18], an event driven SMC was proposed for a chemical reactor. A Sliding mode observer based control has been implemented in [19] for a fermentation process and in [20] for a batch polymerization reactor. In [21], a SMC was suggested for temperature control of a batch process. In [22],

a decentralised SMC was developed for the control of two-input-two-output chemical reactor. A temperature trajectory tracking SMC has been designed for a batch reactor [23].

The time-varying Parameters in chemical processes add more difficulties to the control design. An adaptive SMC based support vector machine was designed for a chemical reactor in [24]. In [25], a model free adaptive controller has been constructed to control molecular weight distribution in styrene polymerization. In [26], an adaptive control technique was implemented for a nonlinear wiener model and it was applied for composition control in a chemical reactor. Nonetheless, adaptive control schemes are limited to systems with constant or slow time varying parameters. This limitation can be lifted by deploying neural network (NN) to approximate the system dynamics. A NN based MPC was used for temperature control of a multi-product batch reactor [27]. A RBFNN based internal model controller was utilised to control the average molecular weight in the free radical polymerization of MMA. A NN based generic model control was developed for a multivariable semi-batch reactor [28]

Considering the foregoing discussion, in this paper, we integrate backstepping, fractional order nonsingular terminal sliding mode surface, and adaptive reaching laws to control the monomer concentration and the temperature of a polymerization reactor with uncertain dynamics. Furthermore, this is the first time a ABFNTSMC is proposed to control the reactor. The main contributions of this article include

1. In order to improve the robustness against disturbances, a FNTSM surface has been proposed. Moreover, by combining the FNTSMC with backstepping, the tracking accuracy is greatly enhanced.
2. In [18]-[23], the upper bounds of the disturbances are known. However, chemical processes have multiple operating points and therefore it is difficult to obtain the upper bounds of the dynamic disturbances at each operating region. As a result, we used adaptive laws to estimate the upper bounds of the disturbances. In addition, fast terminal reaching laws are utilised to do away with chattering effects.
3. A Lyapunov candidate function is used to show the convergence and the stability of the closed loop system.

The structure of the paper is arranged as follows: In Section 2 the dynamic model of the polymerization reactor is provided. In Section 3, the proposed control technique is developed. Simulation results and performance comparisons are provided in Section 4. Finally, we conclude our work in Section 5.

2. Mathematical Model

We consider the free radical polymerization of styrene monomers initiated by azobis-iso-butyronitrile dissolved in a pure benzene in a jacketed continuous stirred tank reactor depicted in Fig. 1. The heat released by the exothermic process is removed by a cooling jacket using water as the cooling fluid. The dynamic model of the reactor is derived from material and energy balance equations as [29]

Fig. 1: A simple schematic diagram of the polymerization reactor

$$\dot{x}_1 = -(k_p + k_{fm})\zeta_0 x_1 + \frac{F_m(C_m - x_1)}{v}. \quad (1)$$

$$\dot{x}_2 = -k_I x_2 + \frac{F_I C_I - F x_2}{v}. \quad (2)$$

$$\dot{x}_3 = k_p \frac{(-\Delta H_p)}{\rho c_p} x_1 \zeta_0 - \frac{UA}{\rho c_p v} (x_3 - x_4) + \frac{F(T_{in} - x_3)}{v}. \quad (3)$$

$$\dot{x}_4 = \frac{F_c T_c - F x_4}{v_c} + \frac{UA}{\rho_c c_c v_c} (x_3 - x_4). \quad (4)$$

$$\zeta_0 = \left[\frac{2fk_I}{k_{Tc} + k_{Td}} \right]^{1/2} \sqrt{x_2}.$$

$$M = x_1; T = x_3. \quad (5)$$

where x_1 (kmol/m³), x_2 (kmol/m³) denote the monomer and the initiator concentrations respectively, x_3 (°K) and x_4 (°K) stand for the reactor and the coolant's temperatures respectively. The outputs are $M = x_1$ and $T = x_3$. The inputs are the coolant flow rate F_c m³/h and the initiator flow rate F_I m³/h. The definition and the values of the reactor parameters are given in Table 1.

2.1 Preliminaries

Definition 1 [30] The general definition of the fractional order derivative and integration is given by

$$\theta \mathcal{D}_t^\mu = \begin{cases} \frac{d^\mu}{dt^\mu} & \text{Re}(\mu) > 0. \\ 1 & \text{Re}(\mu) = 0. \\ \int_\theta^t d\tau^\mu & \text{Re}(\mu) < 0. \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

where \mathcal{D} is the fractional calculus operator, μ represents the fractional order which can be complex or real, θ and t stand for the lower and upper limits of the

Table 1: The definitions and values of the reactor parameters [29]

Symbols	Values	Meaning
v	1.0m ³	Reactor volume
T	335K	Reactor temperature
F	10.0m ³ /h	Monomer flow rate
f^*	0.58	Initiator efficiency
k_p	2.50 × 10 ⁶ m ³ /(kmol. h)	Propagation rate constant
k_{Tc}	1.33 × 10 ¹⁰ m ³ /(kmol. h)	Termination by coupling rate constant
k_{Td}	1.09 × 10 ¹¹ m ³ /(kmol. h)	Termination by disproportionation rate constant
C_m	6.00kmol/m ³	Inlet monomer concentration
C_I	8.00kmol/m ³	Inlet monomer concentration
K_I	1.02 × 10 ⁻¹ h ⁻¹	Initiation rate constant
$k_{fm\ rl}$	2.45 × 10 ³ m ³ /(kmol. h)	Chain transfer to monomer rate constant
M_m	100.12 kg/kmol	Molecular weight of the monomer

ρ	866kgm ³	Density of the reacting mixture
$\rho_c r r_1$	1000 kg. m ³	Density of water
c_p	2.0 kJ/kg ⁻¹ · K ⁻¹	Heat capacity of the reacting mixture
$-\Delta H_p$	57800kJ. kmol ⁻¹	Heat of propagation reaction
U	720kJ. h ⁻¹ · K ⁻¹	Overall heat transfer coefficient
A	2.0m ²	Heat transfer area
c_c	4.2kj. kg ⁻¹ · K ⁻¹	Heat capacity of water
T_{in}	350K	Temperature of the inlet streams in the reactor
T_c	293.2K	Temperature of the inlet coolant stream

operation, $\text{Re}(\mu)$ represents the real part μ . The Riemann-Liouville definition of the fractional-order calculus is given by

$${}_{\theta} \mathcal{D}_t^{\mu} = \left(\frac{d}{dt}\right)^n \frac{1}{\Gamma(n-\mu)} \int_{\theta}^t \frac{f(\tau)}{(t-\tau)^{\mu-n+1}} d\tau \quad (7)$$

$n - 1 < \mu < n, n \in \mathcal{N}, \mu \in \mathcal{R}$ and $\Gamma(\cdot)$ is gamma function

Assumption 1 The disturbances are bounded $\Delta_i \leq K_i (i = m, T)$

By differentiating M and T from (5) with respect to time, we have

$$\begin{cases} \dot{M} = \frac{\partial M}{\partial x_1} \dot{x}_1 + \frac{\partial M}{\partial x_2} \dot{x}_2 \\ \dot{T} = \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_1} \dot{x}_1 + \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_2} \dot{x}_2 + \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_3} \dot{x}_3 + \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_4} \dot{x}_4 \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

Differentiating (8) with respect to time yields

$$\begin{cases} \ddot{M} = \frac{\partial(\dot{M})}{\partial x_1} \dot{x}_1 + \frac{\partial(\dot{M})}{\partial x_2} \dot{x}_2 \\ \ddot{T} = \frac{\partial(\dot{T})}{\partial x_1} \dot{x}_1 + \frac{\partial(\dot{T})}{\partial x_2} \dot{x}_2 + \frac{\partial(\dot{T})}{\partial x_3} \dot{x}_3 + \frac{\partial(\dot{T})}{\partial x_4} \dot{x}_4 \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

It is obvious that the inputs can be extracted from (9). Therefore

$$\begin{cases} \ddot{M} = A_1(x) + B_{11}(x)F_i \\ \ddot{T} = A_2(x) + B_{21}(x)F_i + B_{22}(x)F_c \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

where:

$$\begin{aligned} A_1(x) &= \frac{\partial(\dot{M})}{\partial x_1} \dot{x}_1 + \frac{\partial(\dot{M})}{\partial x_2} \left[-k_1 x_2 + \frac{-F x_2}{v} \right] \\ A_2(x) &= \frac{\partial(\dot{T})}{\partial x_1} \dot{x}_1 + \frac{\partial(\dot{T})}{\partial x_2} \left[-k_1 x_2 + \frac{-F x_2}{v} \right] \\ &\quad + \frac{\partial(\dot{T})}{\partial x_3} \dot{x}_3 + \frac{\partial(\dot{T})}{\partial x_4} \left[\frac{-F x_4}{v_c} + \frac{UA(x_3 - x_4)}{\rho_c c_c v_c} \right] \\ B_{11}(x) &= \frac{C_l}{v} \frac{\partial(\dot{M})}{\partial x_2}, \quad B_{21}(x) = \frac{\partial(\dot{T})}{\partial x_2} \frac{C_l}{v} \\ B_{22}(x) &= \frac{\partial(\dot{T})}{\partial x_4} \frac{T_c}{v_c}, \quad U_1 = F_i, \quad U_2 = F_c \end{aligned}$$

From (10), we have

$$\begin{cases} \dot{\xi}_1 = \xi_2 \\ \dot{\xi}_2 = A(x) + B(x)U + \Delta \end{cases} \quad \# \quad (11)$$

where

$$\xi_1 = \begin{bmatrix} M_1 \\ T_1 \end{bmatrix}, \xi_2 = \begin{bmatrix} M_2 \\ T_2 \end{bmatrix}, A(x) = \begin{bmatrix} A_1(x) \\ A_2(x) \end{bmatrix},$$

$$U = \begin{bmatrix} U_1 \\ U_2 \end{bmatrix}, \Delta = \begin{bmatrix} \Delta_1 \\ \Delta_2 \end{bmatrix}, B(x) = \begin{bmatrix} B_{11}(x) & 0 \\ B_{21}(x) & B_{22}(x) \end{bmatrix}.$$

where Δ denotes the external disturbances. $B^{-1}(x)$ exists since $\det(B(x)) = B_1(x)B_2(x) \neq 0$.

3. Control design

In this section, the proposed AB-FNTSMC is developed for the control of monomer concentration and reactor temperature. In addition, a robust backstepping with integral sliding mode controller (RBISMC) and feedback linearization controller (FLC) are designed for comparison with the AB-FNTSMC.

3.1 Design of AB-FNTSMC

The tracking errors are expressed as

$$z_1 = \xi_1 - \xi_d; \dot{z}_1 = \dot{\xi}_1 - \dot{\xi}_d = \xi_2 - \dot{\xi}_d.$$

$$z_2 = \xi_2 - \dot{\xi}_d; \dot{z}_2 = \dot{\xi}_2 - \ddot{\xi}_d$$

where $z_1 = [z_m \ z_T]^T$, $z_2 = [\dot{z}_m \ \dot{z}_T]^T$ are the vectors of tracking errors and $\xi_d = [M_d \ T_d]^T$ is the vector of the desired trajectories. The FNTSM surface is specified as [31]

$$S = z_2 + \Lambda_1 D^{\mu_1} [\text{sign}(z_1)^p] + \Lambda_2 D^{\mu_2-1} [\text{sign}(z_1)^q]. \quad (12)$$

where

$$S = \begin{bmatrix} S_M \\ S_T \end{bmatrix}; \Lambda_1 = \begin{bmatrix} \Lambda_{1m} & 0 \\ 0 & \Lambda_{1T} \end{bmatrix}; \Lambda_2 = \begin{bmatrix} \Lambda_{2m} & 0 \\ 0 & \Lambda_{2T} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\text{sign}(z_1)^p = \begin{bmatrix} \text{sign}(z_m)^p \\ \text{sign}(z_T)^p \end{bmatrix}; \text{sign}(z_1)^q = \begin{bmatrix} \text{sign}(z_m)^q \\ \text{sign}(z_T)^q \end{bmatrix}.$$

The time derivative of the sliding surface (12) yields

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{S} &= \dot{z}_2 + \Lambda_1 D^{\mu_1+1} [\text{sign}(z_1)^p] + \Lambda_2 D^{\mu_2} [\text{sign}(z_1)^q] \\ &= \dot{\xi}_2 - \ddot{\xi}_d + \Lambda_1 D^{\mu_1+1} [\text{sign}(z_1)^p] + \Lambda_2 D^{\mu_2} [\text{sign}(z_1)^q]. \\ &= A(x) + B(x)U + \Delta - \ddot{\xi}_d + \Lambda_1 D^{\mu_1+1} [\text{sign}(z_1)^p] \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

Select a Lyapunov function as

$$L_1 = \frac{1}{2} z_1^T z_1. \quad (14)$$

$$\dot{L}_1 = z_1^T \dot{z}_1 = z_1^T (\dot{\xi}_1 - \dot{\xi}_d) = z_1^T (\xi_2 - \dot{\xi}_d). \quad (15)$$

The virtual controller is designed as

$$\xi_2 = \dot{\xi}_d - Cz_1 - S. \quad (16)$$

where $C = C^T > 0$ is a constant diagonal matrix. Inserting the virtual input (16) into (14) gives

$$\dot{L}_1 = -z_1^T Cz_1 + z_1^T S \quad (17)$$

Consider the following Lyapunov function

$$L_2 = \frac{1}{2} z_1^T z_1 + \frac{1}{2} S^T S \tag{18}$$

Differentiating (18) with respect to time, we have

$$\dot{L}_2 = z_1^T \dot{z}_1 + S^T \dot{S} = -z_1^T C z_1 + S^T (z_1 + \dot{S}) \tag{19}$$

where

$$r = -\ddot{\xi}_d + \Lambda_1 D^{\mu+1} [\text{sign}(z_1)^p] + \Lambda_2 D^{\mu_2} [\text{sign}(z_1)^q]$$

To guarantee fast convergence and excellent tracking accuracy with the existence of model perturbations and disturbances, a FTSM reaching law is developed as

$$\dot{S} = -B(x)^{-1} [R_1 S + R_2 \text{sign}(S)^\vartheta]. \tag{20}$$

where $\text{sign}(S)^\vartheta = [\text{sign}(S_M)^\vartheta, \text{sign}(S_T)^\vartheta]^T$, R_1 and R_2 are unknown constant diagonal matrices. Therefore, the robust controller can be written as

$$U = B^{-1}(x) [-z_1 - A(x) - r - \hat{R}_1 S - \hat{R}_2 \text{sign}(S)^\vartheta]. \tag{21}$$

where \hat{R}_i is the estimate matrices $\hat{R}_i (i = 1, 2)$. The matrices are estimated by the following adaptation laws

$$\begin{cases} \dot{\hat{R}}_1 = \alpha_1 [\text{diag}(S)^T \text{diag}(S) - \kappa_1 \hat{R}_1]. \\ \dot{\hat{R}}_2 = \alpha_2 [\text{diag}(S)^T \text{diag}(\text{sign}(S)^\vartheta) - \kappa_1 \hat{R}_2]. \end{cases} \tag{22}$$

where $\alpha_1 = \alpha_1^T > 0, \alpha_2 = \alpha_2^T > 0$ are constant diagonal matrices, $\kappa_1 > 0, \kappa_2 > 0$ are small constants.

Theorem 1 For the input-output dynamics (11) under the FNFTSM surface (12), if the adaptive control law is established as (21) updated with (22), then, S, z_1, z_2, \hat{R}_1 , and \hat{R}_2 are ultimately uniformly bounded.

Proof By augmenting the Lyapunov function (18), we get

$$L_2 = \frac{1}{2} z_1^T z_1 + \frac{1}{2} S^T S + \frac{1}{2} \tilde{R}_1^T \alpha_1^{-1} \tilde{R}_1 + \frac{1}{2} \tilde{R}_2^T \alpha_2^{-1} \tilde{R}_2. \tag{23}$$

Differentiating (23) with respect to time, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{L}_2 &= z_1^T \dot{z}_1 + S^T \dot{S} + \tilde{R}_1^T \alpha_1^{-1} \dot{\tilde{R}}_1 + \tilde{R}_2^T \alpha_2^{-1} \dot{\tilde{R}}_2 \\ &= -z_1^T C z_1 + S^T (z_1 + A(x) + B(x)U + \Delta + r) \end{aligned} \tag{24}$$

Substituting the control input (21) into (24), one has

$$\dot{L}_2 = -z_1^T C z_1 + S^T (\Delta - \hat{R}_1 S - \hat{R}_2 \text{sign}(S)^\vartheta) \tag{25}$$

Noting that $\hat{R}_i = R_i - \tilde{R}_i (i = 1, 2)$, we achieve

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{L}_2 &= -z_1^T C z_1 + S^T (\Delta - R_1 S - R_2 \text{sign}(S)^\vartheta) \\ &\quad + \tilde{R}_1 [\text{diag}(S)^T \text{diag}(S) - \alpha_1^{-1} \dot{\tilde{R}}_1] \end{aligned} \tag{26}$$

Substituting the update laws(22) into (26) yields

$$\dot{L}_2 = -z_1^T C z_1 - S^T R_1 S + S^T R_0 \text{sign}(S)^\vartheta \tag{27}$$

where $R_0 = [\text{diag}(\Delta) \text{diag}^{-1}(\text{sign}(S)^\vartheta) - R_2]$. Using the following Young's inequalities,

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{R}_i \hat{R}_i &= \tilde{R}_i [R_i - \tilde{R}_i] \leq \frac{\|R_i\|^2}{2} - \frac{\|\tilde{R}_i\|^2}{2} (i = 1, 2) \\ S^T R_1 S &\leq \|S\|^2 \|R_1\|; S^T R_0 \text{sign}(S)^\vartheta \leq \|S\|^{1+\vartheta} \|R_0\|; \\ \|S\|^{2(1+\vartheta)} \|R_0\|^2 &\leq \|S\|^2 \|R_0\|^2, \|S\|^2 \rightarrow 0 \end{aligned}$$

Equation (27) can be written as

$$\dot{L} \leq -m \left[\frac{\|z_1\|^2}{2} + \frac{\|S\|^2}{2} + \frac{\|\tilde{R}_1\|^2}{2\|\alpha_1\|} + \frac{\|\tilde{R}_2\|^2}{2\|\alpha_2\|} \right]$$

$$+ \frac{\|R_1\|^2}{2} + \frac{\|R_2\|^2}{2} \tag{28}$$

Therefore,

$$L \leq -mL + n. \tag{29}$$

where $m = \min\{\|C\|, 2(\|R_1\| - \|R_3\|)\kappa\|\alpha_1\|, \kappa\|\alpha_2\|\}$, $n = \frac{\|R_1\|^2}{2} + \frac{\|R_2\|^2}{2}$. Integrating (28) yields

$$L \leq \frac{n}{m} + L(0)e^{-mt}. \tag{30}$$

As $t \rightarrow \infty$, $L \leq \frac{n}{m}$. Therefore, the closed loop signals are uniformly ultimately bounded in the compact set $\beta = \{L: L \leq \frac{n}{m}\}$

3.2 Design of RBISM

The ISM surface is defined as [32]

$$S = z_2 + \Pi_1 \int z_1 dt. \tag{31}$$

where $\Pi_1 = \Pi_1^T > 0$ is a constant diagonal matrices. The fictitious controller is designed as

$$\xi_2 = \dot{\xi}_d - C_2 z_1 - S. \tag{32}$$

where $C_2 = C_2^T > 0$ is a diagonal matrix. The control input is developed as

$$\begin{cases} U = U_{eq} + U_r. \\ U_{eq} = B^{-1}(x)[-A(x) + \dot{\xi}_d - z_1 - \Pi_1 z_1]. \\ U_r = -B^{-1}(x)R_3 \text{sign}(S). \end{cases} \tag{33}$$

where $R_3 = R_3^T > 0$ is a diagonal matrix

Theorem 2 For the input-output dynamics (10) controlled by (32) and (33) under the ISM surface (31), then the system is asymptotically stable.

Proof We consider the Lyapunov function

$$L_3 = \frac{1}{2} z_1^T z_1 + \frac{1}{2} S^T S. \tag{34}$$

By computing the time-derivative of (34), one gets

$$\dot{L}_3 = z_1^T \dot{z}_1 + S^T \dot{S} = z_1^T (\xi_2 - \dot{\xi}_d). \tag{35}$$

$$+ S^T (A(x) + B(x)U + \Delta - \ddot{\xi}_d + \Pi_1 z_1).$$

Using the virtual controller (32), one has

$$\dot{L}_3 = -z_1^T C_2 z_1 + S^T [z_1 + A(x) + B(x)U + \Delta] \tag{36}$$

From the control law (33), (36) becomes

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{L}_3 &= -z_1^T C_2 z_1 + S^T [\Delta - R_3 \text{sign}(S)] \\ &\leq -\|C_2\| \|z_1\|^2 - \|S\| [\|R_3 - \text{diag}(\Delta)\|] \end{aligned} \tag{37}$$

where $\tilde{R}_3 = R_3 - \text{diag}(\Delta) > 0$.

3.3 Design of FLC

Equation (10) can be rewritten as

$$\begin{bmatrix} \ddot{M} \\ \ddot{T} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A_1(x) \\ A_2(x) \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} B_{11}(x) & 0 \\ B_{21}(x) & B_{22}(x) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} U_1 \\ U_2 \end{bmatrix}. \tag{38}$$

The global feedback linearization input is thus

$$U = \begin{bmatrix} U_1 \\ U_2 \end{bmatrix} = - \begin{bmatrix} B_{11}(x) & 0 \\ B_{21}(x) & B_{22}(x) \end{bmatrix}^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} A_1(x) \\ A_2(x) \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \Omega_1 \\ \Omega_2 \end{bmatrix}. \tag{39}$$

where Ω_i ($i = 1, 2$) are auxiliary inputs. If $A_i(x), B_i(x)$ ($i = 1, 2$) are completely available, using (39), (38) becomes

$$\begin{cases} \ddot{M} = \Omega_1. \\ \ddot{T} = \Omega_2. \end{cases} \quad (40)$$

Then, the linearized system is thus

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{M}_1 \\ \dot{M}_2 \\ \dot{T}_1 \\ \dot{T}_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} M_1 \\ M_2 \\ T_1 \\ T_2 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \Omega_1 \\ \Omega_2 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (41)$$

Therefore, the auxiliary controller is chosen as

$$\begin{cases} \Omega_1 = \ddot{M}_d + R_{pM}z_M + R_{iM} \int z_M dt + R_{dM} \frac{dz_M}{dt}. \\ \Omega_2 = \ddot{T}_d + R_{pT}z_T + R_{iT} \int z_T dt + R_{dT} \frac{dz_T}{dt}. \end{cases} \quad (42)$$

where R_{pj} , R_{ij} , and R_{dj} ($j = M, T$) are the proportional, integral and derivative gains.

Table 2: The control parameters

Controllers	Values
AB-FNTSMC	$\Lambda_1 = \text{diag} (2.4,3.7), \Lambda_2 = \text{diag} (1.1,2.6)$ $\mu_1 = \mu_2 = 0.9, p = 0.5, q = 1.5$ $C = \text{diag} (13,22)$ $\alpha_1 = \text{diag} (0.05,0.01), \alpha_2 = \text{diag} (0.9,4)$
RBISMC	$\Pi_1 = \text{diag} (18,30), C_2 = \text{diag} (8,15)$ $R_3 = \text{diag} (12,16)$
FLC	$R_{pM} = 21, R_{dM} = 13, R_{iM} = 3$ $R_{pT} = 14, R_{dT} = 9, R_{iT} = 1.6$

4. Simulation results

In this section, simulation results are provided to show the satisfactory performance of the AB-FNTSMC designed. In addition, the Proposed AB-FNTSMC is compared with RBISMC and FLC. The parameters of the reactor are given in Table 1. The states of the process are simulated with an initial value of $x_i(0) = 0.001$ ($i = 1,2,3,4$). A model uncertainty of 30% and external disturbances $\Delta_1 = 2, \Delta_2 = 18$ have been considered in the simulation. The parameters of the controllers are provided in Table 2.

The simulation results for the polymerization reactor control are presented In Figs. 2-6. As shown in Fig. 2, the FLC failed to trace the reference trajectories in the presence of dynamic uncertainties. Due to the robustness of the RBISMC, it is able compensate the uncertainties and track the reference signals. The responses of the outputs under the AB-FNTSMC are superior compared to both FLC and RBISMC due to its adaptive nature and robustness of the FNTSM surface. The tracking errors depicted in Fig. 3 converge to zero at a quicker rate under the AB-FNTSMC. The control signals of the AB-FNTSMC have no chattering unlike the RBISMC as shown in 4. The evolution of the parameters of reaching laws are shown in Fig. 5 and Fig. 6.

5. Conclusions

A robust AB-FNTSMC scheme for an uncertain polymerization reactor is developed in this article. The proposed controller admits strong robustness against external disturbances and uncertain model parameters. The chattering phenomena have been eliminated with the aid of fast terminal reaching laws with adaptive gains. Finally, some simulations have been executed to illustrate the efficiency of the devised method compared to FLC and RBISMC.

Fig. 2: Outputs' tracking

Fig. 3: Position tracking result

Fig. 4: The control inputs

Fig. 5: Elements of the matrix R_1

Fig. 6: Elements of the matrix R_2

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